

Polarographic Reduction of Some 5,5-Dimethylcyclohexane-2-Benzothiazolyldiazono-1,3-Diones and its 2-Methyl, 4-Methyl, 4-Methoxy, 4-Ethoxy Derivatives

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Polarographic studies of some 5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-2-benzothiazolyldiazono-1,3-diones were carried out in B. R. buffer in the pH range 2.0-12.0. All the compounds gave a single, well defined, irreversible, diffusion controlled reduction wave whose $E_{1/2}$ was pH dependent but i_d remained constant throughout the entire pH range. The $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards negative potential with increase in pH, thereby showing that protonation precedes reduction. The effect of the double layer structure on the $E_{1/2}$ is also studied.

MOST of the polarographic investigations on sulphur containing organic compounds deal with -SH, -S-S-, $R_2N-C \begin{matrix} \diagup S \\ \diagdown S \end{matrix}$, -NH-CS-NH-, -NH-CS-S- and RSO_3H groups¹⁻⁴ but not much has been done to study the polarography of other classes of sulphur containing organic compounds such as thiazoles and benzothiazoles⁵⁻⁷ which are of great biological importance. A knowledge of their redox behaviour at the solution-mercury interface may prove useful from physiological point of view. Moreover, the polarographic behaviour of hydrazones has received little attention⁸⁻⁹ and little information is available about the hydrazones in which the carbon atom of the -NH-N=C- group is attached to cyclohexane ring. Polarographic studies on the reduction of these compounds at DME were therefore undertaken. The present paper describes the results of such studies on some recently synthesised diazono derivatives of 2-aminobenzothiazoles (A).

Experimental

Apparatus: The polarographic measurements were carried out using a Cambridge pen recording polarograph. The capillary characteristic was $2.040 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$. SCE was used as the reference electrode. pH measurements were made with an expanded scale ECIL pH-meter in connection with glass electrodes. The polarograms were recorded at $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Reagents and solutions: 5,5-Dimethylcyclohexane-2-benzothiazolyldiazono-1,3-diones having

substituents H, 2- CH_3 , 4- CH_3 , 4- OCH_3 and 4- OC_2H_5 , were prepared according to the method developed earlier¹⁰ and their purity was assured by repeated recrystallisation. Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.0-12.0 were prepared by adding requisite amount of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide solution to stock acid solution composed of boric acid, phosphoric acid and acetic acid. The chemicals used were of A. R. grade. Stock solution ($1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) of hydrazones were prepared in dimethylformamide.

Procedure: Solutions for recording polarograms were prepared by mixing 3.0 ml hydrazone solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$), 1.0 ml 1.0 M KCl and 6.0 ml buffer. The polarograms were then recorded after passing hydrogen for about 10 min. The number of electrons involved in the reduction process were calculated by millicoulometry method¹¹ using CdSO_4 solution as reference. The controlled potential electrolysis was carried out at potential corresponding to the plateau (1.6 V) of the wave. The electrolysis cell was a H-shaped one, the cathodic and anodic compartments being separated by a diaphragm of sintered glass. Mercury was used as electrode material. After complete electrolysis (about 6 hr) the catholyte was analysed for the identification of the end product.

Results and Discussion

The compounds listed in Table I gave a single 4e reduction wave in B. R. buffer of pH 2.0-12.0 and in 0.1 M NaOH. The nature of the wave was found to be diffusion controlled as evident by the linear dependence of limiting current on $\sqrt{h}$ and concentration of depolarizer. The constancy of wave height in the pH range studied, together with the fact that di/dt had a very low value of temperature coefficient further confirmed that the reduction

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TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 5,5-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXANE-2-BENZOTHIASOZOLYLHYDRAZONO-1,3-DIONES AT pH 7.4; CONC. 3.0×10^{-4} M

Sl. No.	R	$-E_{1/2}$, V	i_d , μ_A	I	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$, V/pH	$\frac{V}{pH}$	$\Delta E_{1/2}$, V	αn		P
								I Method*	II Method**	
1	H	0.48	0.85	0.22	0.068	0.00	1.20	1.20	1.22	
2	2-CH ₃	0.56	0.85	0.22	0.066	0.08	1.02	1.07	1.30	
3	4-CH ₃	0.51	0.90	0.23	0.062	0.03	1.08	1.10	1.24	
4	4-OCH ₃	0.51	0.85	0.22	0.062	0.08	1.32	1.28	1.03	
5	4-OC ₂ H ₅	0.52	0.85	0.22	0.061	0.04	1.20	1.24	1.11	

*Log plots method.

**Oldham and Perry method.

waves were fully diffusion controlled. The wave characteristics are shown in Table I.

The half-wave potential of these compounds was found to be dependent on pH and shifted towards more negative potential with increase in pH. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH were linear with slopes in the range 0.061 to 0.066 V/pH upto pH 8.3 and thereafter there was a small change in $E_{1/2}$. The value of the slope was significantly small. The irreversible nature of the waves was confirmed by log plots¹². The fact that $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential with increasing concentration of the depolariser further pointed towards the irreversible nature of the waves. The value of αn_a (product of transfer coefficient and the number of electrons transferred in the rate determining step) and p (number of protons involved during the rate determining step of the reaction) was determined using the expressions¹³

$$E_{1/4} - E_{3/4} = -\frac{0.0517}{\alpha n_a}$$

$$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH} = -\frac{0.05915}{\alpha n_a} \cdot p$$

The values of αn_a was also determined by the method of Oldham and Perry¹³ using the expression

$$E_{1/2} = E_r + \frac{0.0592}{\alpha n_a} \log \left[1.35 K_r + \frac{t}{D} \right]$$

where t is the drop time at the potential E_r . The values of half-wave potentials together with $dE_{1/2}/dpH$, αn_a and p are also given in Table I.

Since the $E_{1/2}$ of these thiazoles were pH dependent and the limiting current pH independent upto pH 8.3, it was concluded that both acidic and basic forms of the compounds reached the electrode surface and are electroactive. Thus, the proton transfer reaction precedes the electrode process in such cases. Out of the two general sequences¹⁴ for the proton and electron addition viz., H^+, e, H^+, e and H^+, e, e, H^+ , the former sequence was more probable for these compounds in the light of their structural genesis. After the uptake of a proton and one electron the radical (C) would accept a proton to form a protonated radical (D) which after taking one electron would get cleaved at the nitrogen bond with the formation of aniline. The imine (F) formed was further protonated and got reduced.

Alternatively, the radical (C) could also combine with an electron instead of proton but this possibility was cancelled out by the fact that such a reduction would involve only 2 electrons whereas polarographic data clearly indicate 4-electron transfer reactions at the DME.

These mechanistic steps found support from the increase of $E_{1/2}$ with pH as protons are consumed in reduction. As the rate of protonation becomes slow the $E_{1/2}$ tends to become constant. Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH for some 5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-2-benzothiazolylhydrazone-1,3-diones.

shows that above pH 8.3, the shifting of half-wave potential with pH towards negative potential is not so marked as in the acidic range. Moreover, at pH above 8.3, the $E_{1/2}$ is practically constant. In the pH range studied where both the electroactive forms (acidic as well as basic) are reduced, half-wave potential of the two forms are so close that the waves merge and no separation is observed.

Similar steps for the reduction of hydrazone group have also been proposed by others¹⁵⁻¹⁷, involving cleavage of the nitrogen-nitrogen bond.

Due to an acid-base equilibrium that exists between two structural forms of the compounds, wave height of the wave remains pH independent as long as the formation of the acidic form from the basic form is fast enough. When pH increases the rate of protonation decreases and the wave height decreases as well.

When the depolariser solution was tested after controlled potential electrolysis, it gave dye test thereby showing that at least one of the reduction product is aromatic amine. UV spectra of the solution during electrolysis were recorded at different intervals of time. λ_{max} CH_3OH at 415 nm for $-\text{NH}-\text{N}=\text{C}-$ grouping showed a decrease in the peak height after each interval of time and finally disappeared, confirming the above reduction mechanism.

Effect of supporting electrolyte concentration : The effect of the double layer structure on the $E_{1/2}$ of a process preceded by the protonation is given by the equation¹³,

$$\Delta E_{1/2} \approx \Delta \psi_1 \left(\frac{\alpha n_a - Z}{\alpha n_a} - \frac{\partial E_{1/2}}{\partial \text{pH}} \frac{F}{2.30 RT} \right) \dots (1)$$

where ψ_1 is the variation in the double layer potential, α the transfer coefficient, n_a the number of electrons transferred in the rate determining step and Z the charge of the particle being discharged. Undoubtedly, a marked effect of change in ionic strength on $E_{1/2}$ should be observed in cases where the depolarizer is in the ionic form and no such effect should be observed if it is in the non-ionic form, i.e., $Z=0$. Since the second term in the bracket of equation (1) is nearly -1 and $Z=0$, $E_{1/2}$ will be almost independent of ψ_1 or of ionic strength. This was verified by carrying out experiments with varying concentrations of KCl (0.01 M to 0.25 M). The values of $dE_{1/2}/d\text{pH}$ thus obtained fell in the range 60-70 mV/pH and $E_{1/2}$ and i_d remained unaffected by the change in concentration of the supporting electrolyte.

Effect of solvent composition : The polarogram of the above mentioned thiazoles were recorded in the minimum amount of DMF (20%) necessary for the dissolution of the compound. The DMF percentage was then progressively increased from 20 to 60% to see the effect of solvent composition on the electrode process.

$E_{1/2}$ of the compounds was found to shift towards more negative potential almost linearly¹⁰ and that this effect is much more pronounced in compounds having comparatively more positive potential. This shift may be attributed¹⁰ to a decrease in the surface concentration of the electroactive species in addition to a change of pH and pK_a of the protonated depolarizer.

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